

EFFECT OF NANOCCLAY CLUSTERS IN MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF NANOCCLAY/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The mechanical and thermal properties of nanoclay polymer composites have been experimentally investigated over the last decade. Most of the research has been focused mainly on the control of their inter-planar structures, which govern the global properties of the composites. In reality, these structures (both exfoliated and intercalated patterns) are hardly achieved in the manufacturing process of products. Different sizes of clusters mixed by the nanoclay and matrix would be easily formed, particularly in the extrusion of polymer-based components. This paper experimentally studied the influence of micro-hardness of nanoclay/epoxy composites with different amount of nanoclay content, which formed different sizes of the clusters. The results showed that the micro-hardness of the composites could be enhanced when a small amount of nanoclay was used. However, there was an optimal limit in which the hardness was dropped with continuously increasing the nanoclay content. Microscopic observation on the fracture surfaces showed that the size of the clusters varied with the amount of nanoclays used in the composites.

KEYWORDS: Product Development; Nanoclays; Nanocomposites; Hardness.

INTRODUCTION

Clay/polymer nanocomposites have provided an efficient upgrade on the mechanical and thermal performances of conventional polymer-based composites with mixing a relatively small amount of layered silicates (hereafter called “nanoclays”), typically in the range of 3 – 5 wt.% [1,2]. In the industrial point of view, these lightest particles could be effectively used to produce high stiffness and economical structural components without having the subjection of weight penalty. Many product manufacturing organizations and commercial companies have started to deeply investigate the development and production of this type of nanocomposites in order to fabricate materials with high strength and thermal stability for product development [3-5]. However, these properties are highly dependent on the uniformity of dispersion associated with controlled planar arrangements of nanoclays into matrix [6]. It has been reported that the impact and wear resistance, and fracture toughness of the composites could be improved by adding an optimal amount of nanoparticles into polymer-based composites [7-9]. The optimum amount of nanoparticles in the composites depends on the filler size, shape, homogeneity of particle distribution and the interfacial bonding properties between the fillers and matrix. Practically, both exfoliated and intercalated planar structures can only be found in the laboratory study, it is in fact difficult to achieve during plastic moulding process. Alternatively, the formation of micro-size nanoclay/polymer clusters always appears in the composites. These clusters, in turn, would influence the intrinsic material and mechanical properties of the composites. Based on the best

knowledge from the authors, there is no detailed study on the hardness of nanoclay/polymer composites due to the influence of these clusters to date.

In this paper, nanoclay/epoxy composite samples were made with different amount of nanoclay particles. The micro-hardness of the samples was examined using Micro-hardness tester (Vicker type). The microscopic observation on the fractured surface of these samples was also conducted to measure the cluster size and their effect to the hardness of the composites. In accompany with the investigation of the micro-hardness properties by the cluster effect of the nanoclay composite, the three-point bending results will be also used to interpret the cluster size effect on the strength and toughness of the nanoclay composites.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Araldite GY 251 epoxy resin mixed with hardener HY 956 in the ratio of 5:1 to form base materials and nanoclay particles (SiO_2 , Nanolin DK1 series from the Zhejiang FH Nanoclay Chemical Technology Company) were then added into the materials to form nanoclay/epoxy nanocomposites. The mean diameter, density and moisture content of the nanoclays were 25 nm, less than 3% and 0.45 g/cm^3 with more than 95% of SiO_2 , respectively. At the beginning of the nanocomposite manufacturing process, the predetermined amount of nanoclays were added into the resin by hand stirring and followed by sonication for 1 hr at room temperature. The hardener was then added into the mixtures by mechanical stirring and followed by vacuuming for another 24 hrs for curing. Six types of sample were made in this study; they were pure epoxy (0 wt.% nanoclay), and nanocomposites with 2 wt.%, 4 wt. %, 6 wt.%, 10 wt.% and 15 wt. % of nanoclays. Micro-hardness test was conducted to all samples and a total of ten indentation points were measured on the samples' surface. Micro-hardness tester (FM-7E) of the Future-Test Corporation from Tokyo, Japan was used in the test. To increase the accuracy of measurement, all sample's surfaces were well polished using high-grade sandpapers prior to the test. To observe the dispersion properties of the nanocomposites with different amount of nanoclay content, some samples were broken into two pieces by a simple three-point bending test and the fractured surfaces were examined by using Leica Stereoscan 440 model scanning electron microscopy (SEM). X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) was also used to verify the validity of the location of the nanoclay particles (Fig.1).

Fig. 1 Diagrams captured from EDX: location away from the cluster (left) and the center of the cluster (right)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 shows the experimental measurements of micro-hardness of the nanocomposites with different nanoclay contents.

Table 1 Results of the micro-hardness measurements at different nanoclay compositions

Hardness (Hv)	0%	2%	4%	6%	10%	15%
1	9.9	10.8	11.7	11.7	8.2	1.5
2	9.2	11.6	12.9	10.4	5.1	1.5
3	9.6	10.1	11.9	11.1	5.5	2.3
4	9.4	11.9	14.4	10.9	6.2	3.5
5	9.5	12.3	12.8	12.9	6.1	5.1
6	10.1	11.8	12.7	12.5	6.1	2.9
7	10.6	10.1	12.1	10.9	4.8	3.2
8	11.4	12.2	13.1	11.8	5.3	2.6
9	10.5	12	13	12	6.1	2.2
10	10.6	11.3	12.9	10.2	6.3	2
Average:	10.08	11.41	12.75	11.44	5.97	2.68
Maximum:	11.4	12.3	14.4	12.9	8.2	5.1
Minimum:	9.2	10.1	11.7	10.2	4.8	1.5

An average hardness was calculated by ten indentation measurements and the plot of the results of each type of samples is shown in Fig.2. It is obvious that the hardness increases with the content of the nanoclay is increased. The peak is located at a sample with 4 wt.% nanoclay. A decline of the hardness also appears if further increasing the nanoclay content; the hardness decreases in a drastic manner from 12.75 Hv (4 wt.% of nanoclay) to 2.68 Hv (15 wt.% of nanoclay). In most previous literatures, it was inducted that adding a small amount of nanoclays

into polymer-based materials could potentially enhance their strength, like hardness of the current sample with the nanoclay content smaller than 4 wt.%. However, it is also reasonable to believe that it should have an optimal limit since the physical properties between these nano-reinforcements and matrix are different. In the current study, it is demonstrated that the hardness was dropped if the amount of the nanoclays was beyond 4 wt.%. By looking at the trend presented in Fig.2, it is worthwhile to detailedly study what is the physical mechanism that governs this contrary effect in hardness of the nanocomposites.

Fig. 2

Average values of the micro-hardness test at different clay compositions

In Figs 3 and 4, the comparison on the fractured surfaces of the samples with and without mixing with nanoclays is shown. It is obvious that clusters were formed in the sample with 4 wt.% nanoclay particles. The average diameter of the clusters measured throughout the whole sample at different locations was about 125 nm. The clusters were evenly distributed throughout the sample, which reflected that those small nanoparticles intended to agglomerate with each other. This phenomenal observation denotes that those nanoclay particles could not be easily dispersed although it was subjected to sonication. This might be due to the viscosity of the room temperature cured resin could not be low enough to diffuse into the planar structures of the nanoclay particles.

Fig. 3 SEM photograph of pure epoxy

Fig. 4 SEM photograph of 4 wt.% of nanoclay/epoxy composites

In Fig.5, a micrograph of the sample with 15 wt.% of nanoclay particles is shown. Comparing with Fig.4, the size of the clusters is apparently bigger than that the one with only 4 wt. % nanoclay particles. The diameter of the sample with 15 wt.% of nanoclay particles measured from the SEM was about 400 nm.

Fig. 5 SEM photograph of 15 wt.% of nanoclay/epoxy composites

This phenomenon is explainable, as the wt.% of the nanoclay increases, the free volume allows for nanoclay particles to move around would be decreased. Therefore, the mechanical stirring and ultrasonic separation techniques can not be effectively used to separate the agglomerations of the nanoclays, as higher the wt.% of nanoclay particles in the epoxy resin, the less the free volume for each nanoclay particles to live in. At the same time, the cross-link density of the nanocomposites then increased and it therefore resulted in increasing the tendency for the nanoclay particles to form pairs or clusters [10]. As the amount of nanoclay particles increases in the composites, the inertia for the nanoclay particles to form agglomerate is also increased. Therefore, larger clusters of nanoclay would be easily formed. The average cluster sizes of nanocomposites with different amount of nanoclay particles is plotted in Fig.6. The cluster size increased with increasing the wt.% of the nanoclay particles.

Fig. 6 Variation of the cluster size at different wt.% of nanoclay

In Figs 7 to 9, the load extension relation of the three-point bending test of the nanocomposites at different nanoclay contents are shown. The load-extension relationship of three-point bending is measured by the onset of applied load and the extension is the displacement from the origin as shown in Fig. 10. In Fig.7, there is a long plastic yielding zone appearing before the final fracture with the maximum load at in the pure epoxy sample. From the long yielding zone of the pure epoxy, this can be explained that the fracture energy consumption and the fracture toughness of the pure epoxy is quite high. In Fig. 8, however, in the 4 wt.% of nanoclay sample, the plastic yielding zone is extremely small, this deduces that the fracture toughness of the epoxy has no improvement on the addition of the nanoclay. On the other hand, the fracture toughness has been adversely affected by the addition of nanoclay. The phenomenon is explainable from the SEM photographs. In the pure epoxy sample, there are no nanoclay clusters formed, the polymer chain of the epoxy thus held together tightly with each other, therefore the energy required to separate them is high. In the 4 wt.% of nanoclay sample, there are tiny nanoclay clusters as shown in Fig. 4. These tiny nanoclay clusters of about 125 nm in diameter will squeeze into the polymer chains of the epoxy and loosen the interaction between each polymer chains. In addition, from the crack surface of the sample, the clusters shape appears like a sphere. From the mirror-like interface between the nanoclay clusters and the epoxy, the interfacial bonding between the nanoclay clusters and the epoxy is weak. As a result, when there is an external force applied, the interface between the nanoclay and the epoxy will be debonded easily. Hence, the fracture toughness of the epoxy is decreased with nanoclay added. At 15 wt.% of nanoclay, the load-extension behaviour appears in a strange way as shown in Fig. 9. It does not possess a clear fracture point after the maximum load appears. This is due to the level of nanoclay content has been greatly increased and the mechanical behaviour is tends to become nanoclay rather than epoxy. As the cluster size becomes larger, the breaking path of the applied load become rougher and more zig-zag. Hence, the fracture toughness of the 15 wt. % of nanoclay becomes higher and more difficult to fracture. In the load-extension curve, the extension of the 15 wt.% sample is quite long and thus it is softer than the one with less nanoclay content.

Fig. 7 Load-extension curve of three-point bending of pure epoxy

Fig. 8 Load-extension curve of three-point bending of 6 wt.% of nanoclay

Fig. 9 Load-extension curve of three-point bending of 15 wt.% of nanoclay

According to the results obtained from the micro-hardness test, the cluster size attributed the properties of the nanocomposites. Increasing the amount of the nanoclay particles in the nanocomposites represents the quantity of the nano-reinforcements is increased, and therefore the

overall strength is also increased. However, it would have an optimal limit since the size of the cluster increases and subsequent the total number of the clusters, as nano/micro-reinforcements is decreased. The distance between these nano-size or micro-size clusters is also decreased which eventually reduces the effectiveness of strengthening the nanocomposites. This is an important aspect since most of previous literatures were mainly focused on the production of exfoliated and intercalated nanoclay structures for nanocomposites. The effect, due to the formation of clusters is normally neglected. However, in real practice, it is extremely difficult to control the nano-structures of the nanoclay particles in the general product manufacturing process. Although the formation of clusters, in some points would induce adverse effects to the product, the use of appropriate amount of nanoclay particles, which produce a pre-determined size of clusters after the manufacturing process, may give optimal mechanical and thermal properties to the whole structures.

CONCLUSION

This paper studies the hardness of nanoclay/epoxy composites with different amount of nanoclay particles. The influence of the hardness due to the formation of clusters is also explained in the paper. Microscopic observation using SEM was conducted to measure the cluster size of the nanocomposites. It was found that the hardness of the nanocomposites increased with increasing the nanoclay content. However, it was also seen that there was an optimal limit. This might be due to the size of the clusters reached a crucial limit and therefore the reinforcing function of the nanoclays decreased. Further works is under processing to detailedly study the mechanical and thermal properties of nanoclay/polymer composites due to formation of clusters.

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